

PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY IN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Creativity is considered as a person's creative professional activity, constructive, non-standard thinking and behavior ability, as well as the ability to understand and develop their experience.

The technology for developing teachers' creative competence is aimed at developing systematic thinking and creative abilities.

This article talks about the scientific-theoretical foundations and pedagogical technologies of creativity development among teachers.

Organization of education based on a systematic approach, a creative module for developing the creative competence of future teachers, and educational technologies are being put into practice in world educational institutions. Systematic works on the qualitative use of knowledge in the preparation of future teachers for professional activities, targeted models of ensuring their methodical preparation, the implementation of multimedia electronic resources in the educational process, and the preparation of future teachers who can design professional activities for creative activities have been carried out. is increasing.

In recent years, the development of didactic conditions for the development of creative competence of students of higher educational institutions, the content of the pedagogical process, development criteria and levels of formation have become important in our republic. Normative bases for creating an electronic monitoring system for the development of creative competence of teachers, implementing local modular technologies, and implementing prognostic models for clarifying the criteria and parameters of creativity assessment were developed. "Further improvement of the continuing education system, increasing the possibilities of quality education services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in line with the modern needs of the labor market" was set as a priority task.

In this regard, the development of the creative competence of future teachers in solving the main requirements of the present day is of urgent importance in educating mature, knowledgeable, creative young people in all respects.

According to researchers, the structure of a teacher's creative competence should consist of professional knowledge, skills, and professional personal qualities. Pedagogical competence includes: "knowledge, skills, as well as a set of methods and tools for their implementation in activity, communication, personal development (self-development). At the same time, the knowledge, skills, qualifications and methods of their implementation do not end the content of this concept. The personal potential of the teacher, the set of personal qualities of creative importance are of great importance."

At this point, it is necessary to pay attention to the consideration of the concept of "creative approach", which is the main factor in the development of creative competence: creative competence is the attitude of the future teacher to creative activity as a combination of ready-made forms available in practice. rather than transformation, as change (development in new complex syntheses according to the characteristics of one's own individuality and the student body), as well as the presence of scientific reflection. It also means the existence of knowledge and ideas about the characteristics and conditions of searching for new ways and means of creative activity, readiness to perceive novelty and the need to create something new. Understanding the creative component is based on the consideration of the phenomenon of creativity, which determines the creative nature of the teacher's creative activity and is manifested at certain stages of the creative-professional process.

Creativity in the "Modern Psychological Dictionary" is "a person's creative abilities (knowledge) that are manifested in a person's thinking, feelings, communication, certain types of activity, describe the person or his separate aspects, activity products, the process of their creation" " is defined as. In the pedagogical dictionary, creativity means the level of creative ability, the ability of creativity, which is a relatively stable characteristic of a person.

There are many definitions of the concept of creativity in foreign literature; this "plurality" can be described by R. Hallman's general statement: "Creative is the combination of perceptions realized in a new way (E. Makellar), the ability to find new connections (L. Kyubi), the emergence of new relationships (K. Rogers), the emergence of new compositions (G. Murray), the tendency to innovate and recognize (G. Lassuel), the activity of the mind leading to new concepts (K. Gerard), the characteristic of experience circulation, new organization (F. Taylor), imagination of new categories of meaning (I. Giselin).

Creativity is the ability to adapt to the need for new approaches and new products. This ability also enables innovation in existence, although the process itself can be both conscious and unconscious. The creation of a new creative product largely depends on the personality of creativity and the strength of its internal motivation. The specific characteristics of the creative process, product, and person are their originality, consistency, relevance to the task, and another characteristic that can be called appropriateness - aesthetic, ecological, optimal form, correct and original at the moment. An attempt is being made to distinguish between the concepts of "creativity" and "creativity". Within such a differentiated approach, creativity is a process and its results, and the definition of creativity refers to its subjective and conditional nature. That is, creativity is a process aimed at creating a new product, and

creativity is the internal potential of a person to go beyond what is known, reject stereotypes in thinking and activity, non-standard, unique thinking ability and others includes

Today, in higher education institutions, the possibility of introducing a clear definition of the teacher's creative competence is due to the rapid development of modern technologies entering the education system, the dynamics of its content, the creative activity of the primary school teacher. is explained by its characteristic. One of the most important problems of modern pedagogy is to determine the optimal pedagogical conditions that help the creative competence and self-development of future teachers, initiative with professional creativity, training of creatively thinking specialists, the ability of creative professional activity, constructive, non-standard thinking and behavior, as well as tasks such as understanding and developing their experience.

The main components of a creative person are:

creative direction (motivational direction and need for creative self-expression, purposeful actions for personally and socially significant results);

creative potential (a set of intellectual and practical competencies, the ability to apply them in defining problems, finding solutions based on intuition and logical thinking, talent in a certain field);

personal psychological identity (willed character traits, emotional stability in overcoming difficulties, self-organization, critical self-esteem, motivated experience of achieved success, material adaptation of oneself to the needs of other people and understanding as a creator of spiritual values).

Thus, the most important condition for the spiritual and socio-economic development of society is education based on a creative approach, the main purpose of which is the formation of a creative personality. The most important link in a teacher's activity is creative pedagogical communication. The development of education based on a creative approach requires the teacher to constantly develop his professional competence, his potential and competitiveness.

There are the following main pedagogical conditions for the successful formation of creative competence of students of a higher educational institution of pedagogy:

1. A positive attitude towards the chosen profession and the presence of a constant need for professional self-improvement (a clear idea about the content of future professional activity; strengthening of professional motivation; involving students in active professionally oriented activities; professional reflection).
2. Activation of creative self-education and self-education (targeted independent work of students on self-improvement; professional self-education; implementation of educational programs of higher education ; professionalization of student teaching).
3. Introducing students to real practical activities in the future specialty (professionalism of higher school teachers; effective management of students' educational, scientific and professional activities; creating a creative environment at the university); teacher's coaching function; positive moral and psychological climate of the educational institution.

In conclusion, it can be said that the mechanisms for the development of creative competence of teachers in higher education institutions, professional development courses,

including group work, creative groups, master classes of teachers, master classes, analysis of passed tests, events at various levels ; active participation in teachers' councils, seminars, conferences; participation in various competitions; participation in scientific and practical conferences; generalization of experience; use of modern methods, forms, teaching tools and new technologies; analyzing and monitoring the teacher's activity; It has been confirmed in the work that it consists of activities such as self-education.

References:

1. Babadjonov S.S. Pedagogik oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarining mediakompetentligini rivojlantirish global ijtimoiy muammo sifatida. – T.: -Pedagogika|| ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal. 2017 yil 2-son, 79 b.
2. G.Ravshanova. Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni kreativ fikrlashga o'rgatish. Innovative Development in Educational Activities. (ISSN:2181-3523) Vol.2.No.5(2023) MARCH 334-340-betlar.
3. G.Ravshanova. O'quvchilarning kreativ fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda mediata'lim texnologiyalarining o'rni. "Pedagogik innovatsiyalar va ularning amaliy tadbiqlari: muammolar va yechimlar" Respublika ilmiyamaliy anjumani (Jizzax shahri, 2022 yil 5-oktabr) 225-231-betlar.
4. A. A. Ismoilov, X. J. Daminov Z. A. Kosimova G. A. Primov "Kreativ fikrlashni baholash". Toshkent- 2021
5. Maftuna, G. (2021). Effective ways to Use Triz (The Theory of Inventive Problem Solving) in Elementary School. Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT, 9, 85-88.
6. Ganieva, M. (2023). EMPOWERING LOGICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH TIPS TECHNOLOGY. In Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education (Vol. 1, No. 12, pp. 62-63).
7. Maftuna, G. (2023). SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS FOR LOGICAL THINKING. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 91-94.